

Date: _____

Appendix 2: Informed Health Choices-Cancer (IHC-C) — Judgement Form (for first round prioritisation)

Instructions: This form includes two parts. In Part 1, please provide us with your personal information; in Part 2, please judge each concept based on your knowledge or experience for inclusion. If you have any comments on any concept, please use the "comments" column.

Part 1: Participant information

Name	
Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Trans-gender <input type="checkbox"/> Non-binary <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____
Date of Birth	Click here to enter a date.
Ethnicity group/background	<u>White</u> <input type="checkbox"/> White Irish <input type="checkbox"/> White Irish Traveller <input type="checkbox"/> Roma <input type="checkbox"/> Any other white background <u>Black or Black Irish</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Black African <input type="checkbox"/> Any other black background <u>Asian or Asian Irish</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Chinese <input type="checkbox"/> Indian/Pakistani/Bangladeshi <input type="checkbox"/> Any other Asian background

	<u>Other, including mixed group/background</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Arabic <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed, write in description: _____ <input type="checkbox"/> Other, write in description: _____
Highest level of (full-time) education/training	<input type="checkbox"/> No formal education <input type="checkbox"/> Primary education <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary education <input type="checkbox"/> Third level (primary degree) <input type="checkbox"/> Third level (postgraduate award)

Part 2: Feedback on each concept

Section 1: claims (be “aware”)

When reviewing each Key Concept please evaluate the following criteria:

	Criteria				Judgements	Comments
Concepts	1. How easy is it to understand this concept?	2. How relevant (i.e., of current significance or importance) do you think this concept is?	3. How likely is it that people are already aware of this concept?	4. How helpful do you think this concept is in supporting people to assess treatment claims or make well-informed choices?	Do you think this concept should be included in an education programme to help people impacted by cancer think critically about the reliability of a treatment claim or make well-informed choices?	

Concept 1	<input type="checkbox"/> very easy	<input type="checkbox"/> very relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> very likely	<input type="checkbox"/> very helpful	<input type="checkbox"/> yes
	<input type="checkbox"/> easy	<input type="checkbox"/> relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> likely	<input type="checkbox"/> helpful	<input type="checkbox"/> no
	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain	<input type="checkbox"/> uncertain	(If no, please state why:
	<input type="checkbox"/> hard	<input type="checkbox"/> irrelevant	<input type="checkbox"/> unlikely	<input type="checkbox"/> unhelpful	<input type="checkbox"/> language; <input type="checkbox"/> readable; <input type="checkbox"/> design
	<input type="checkbox"/> very hard	<input type="checkbox"/> very irrelevant	<input type="checkbox"/> very unlikely	<input type="checkbox"/> very unhelpful	of instructions; others please specify: _____)
Concept 2					
Concept 3					

Any other comments:

Section 2: comparisons (think “fair”)

The same with section 1

Section 3: choices (take care when you decide)

The same with section 1

Thank you for participating!